

A STUDY ON EFFECTIVENESS OF DIGITALIZATION IN RECRUITMENT PROCESS IN PALGHAR DISTRICT

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ABSTRACT

The operating of organization depends upon many components one of which is talent acquisition / recruitment. The goal achievement of organization is based on the success of efforts made by HR department, which evolves through identification and attraction of talented employees generated from recruitment process. Due to advantage in technology e in 20th century there are many parts of recruitment process that has been digitalized. The increased use and dependence of Technology for acquiring/ Identifying talented candidate has drastically changed the way recruitment process was conducted earlier. This is an exploratory type of research with the aim of examining the effectiveness of digital recruitment in palghar district. In this study various types of organization situated in palghar district has been taken as population according to their participation in e-recruitment activities. The paper will discuss the factors that influence HR professional to use digital platform so as to identify and evaluate potential candidates. The findings indicate there are problems like no face to face interaction and attraction of fraud applicants which restrict the use of digital platform for recruitment process. So it is recommended that organizations should use digital platform for faster and accurate hiring of potential candidates.

Keywords: Recruitment, Digitalization, Talent acquisition, digital tools.

INTRODUCTION

Recruitment process is one of the most important human resource function which focuses on attracting the right person with the right blend of skills and experience into the right job and aligning this to the organizations objective. Recruitment is one of the feature of HR which completely depends on speed and accuracy with the increase in number of qualified candidate applying for job. HR professional needs to find way to sort the submitted application quickly and select potential candidate

at right job. New technologies are brought by the professionals to maintain the accuracy and speedy process. Use of digital medium for hiring the potential candidate for the vacant job position is called as e-recruitment.

PROCESS OF E-RECRUITMENT

E-recruitment incorporates all steps of our traditional recruitment process that involve the use of internet-based technology. Here are some important steps of e-recruitment:

- **Posting job advertisement** on online job

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boards to generate large pool of potential candidates.

- **Seeking employee referrals** through Applicant Tracking System. ATS is a Human Resource software application that enables the electronic handling of recruitment and hiring needs. It is used to organize, search, and communicate with large pool of applicants.
- **Sourcing candidates** through professional **social media** or portfolio sites.
- Administer online **pre-employment tests** to evaluate right candidate for the vacant job position.
- Interview candidates using **video interviewing** platform.

- Conduct **background checks** of the candidates through a provider that your ATS integrates with.

It's often said that employees are the biggest assets of the organization. Companies depend on their employee for its success. Recruiting is one such process that brings the right people on board. Well manage recruitment process is very important for the organization to evaluate the best talent which will lead to goal achievement of organization. At present people are extensively adjustable to the technology and that's the reason for popularity of e-recruitment as a practice of talent acquisition.

Following are the two methods adopted by the organization for hiring potential candidates: -

Methods of recruitment followed by the organizations	
TRADITIONAL METHOD	MODERN METHOD
Searching Candidates	
Using non technology supported sources like advertisements, flyers and collecting resumes through walk ins to contact potential applicants.	Using of technology supported sources like organization sources and online job boards to generate large candidate pool.
Screening	
Use of paper-based test to evaluate potential candidate.	Use of online Pre-employment test to reduce the headcount from large pool of candidate.
Interview	
Use of Face to Face conversation to interview which gives personal touch during hiring.	Use of mechanized hiring management system like video interview, telephonic interview etc.
Placement	
Making phone call, setting up the meeting and shaking hands.	Making phone call and sending confirmation letter using e-mail to the selected candidates.

There are many digital tools which has increased the capability of HR professional in this rapidly changing scenario. Digital techniques have become so far the biggest source of external

hires. One of the best feature of Digitalization is accuracy and high performance.

Following are some **e-recruitment tools** used by HR Professionals for recruitment of applicants: -

1) Job Aggregators

It is a search engine which is designed to pull job posting from different site and boards so that all can be viewed at one location. Indeed, CareerBuilder, Google for Jobs are some of the best job aggregators that helps the organization to create large pool of potential candidate.

2) Testing and Assignment

Companies use this bias free hiring assessment to test the knowledge skills abilities and other qualification (KSAOs) of this candidate through digital platform. This tool creates coding and technical assessments which help the organization to evaluate the candidate mainly from technical and engineering background.

3) AI and Automation

Organization believe cognitive computing can drive significant values in HR the competing demand for increase hiring volume and decrease recruiter headcount, an automation is a top digital recruiting tool to screen and shortlist candidate. This tool improves and simplify the experience by its automated assistant software, which helps to schedule meetings and create departmental knowledge base.

4) Video Interview

It is a job interview that takes place remotely & uses video technology as the communication medium. HR managers are currently conducting online interview using video Interviewing tool. It also includes features like text messaging, emails, interview scheduling and automated reference checking.

5) Recruitment CRMs

Candidate relationship management tool become one of the best center for fascinating,

engaging and nurturing candidate in these rising recruitment marketing scenario. This technique is strongest in terms of content marketing.

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

STATEMENT OF PROBLEM

The study focuses on identifying the effectiveness of using digital platform for talent acquisition by the organization by focusing on the benefits, drawbacks and factors that influence the organization to use digitalization in recruitment process.

SOURCES OF DATA COLLECTION

Primary source: - Collection of primary data was done through questionnaire using google forms as a medium of survey.

Secondary source: - Collection of secondary data was done from internet search, past research works, articles and journals.

SAMPLING

A sample of 50 respondents were drawn from companies located in palghar district. Simple random sampling technique has been used to extract data from recruiters from different companies.

OBJECTIVES

- 1) To examine various digital techniques/ tools used in e-recruitment process.
- 2) To identify factors influencing the use of digital recruitment process.
- 3) To understand benefits of using digital recruitment process.
- 4) To identify problems faced by recruiters during digital recruitment process.

DATA ANALYSIS AND INTERPRETATION

Usage of digital tool of recruitment

Use of Digital tool	No. of respondents	Percentage
Yes	44	88%
No	6	12%
Total	50	100%

From the above table we can see that there are 88% of respondents who use digital tools for recruitment process in their organization were as 12% respondents still prefer to follow traditional/old technique for recruiting candidates.

Digital techniques used

Name of digital techniques used	No. of respondents	percentage
Virtual job fairs	8	16%
Social Networks	37	74%
Recruiting blogs	17	34%
Online recruitment sites	37	74%
Video conference	31	62%
Telephonic interviews	39	78%
None	6	12%

From the above table we can see the most used digital technique among the respondents is Telephonic interview with 78%, Social Networks and Online Recruitment Sites with 74% and Video Conference with 62%. We can also see the less used techniques that are Virtual Job Fairs and Recruiting Blogs.

Factors influencing use of Digital techniques

Factors	No. of respondents	percentage
Get the right Position requirements	31	62%
Search and shortlist the right candidates	40	80%
Import Profile from different sources	29	58%
Status update meetings	8	16%
Collect data to create report	23	46%
Interviews and feedback mails and reminders	28	56%
None	6	12%

From the above table we can analyze that Search and Shortlisting the right candidates with 80% is one of the most influential factor that attracts respondents to make use of digital recruitment process. Other that this factors like get the right position requirements with 62% and Import profile from different sources with 58% are highly influential.

Benefits of using Digital Recruitment process

Benefits	No. of respondents	percentage
Cost-effective	25	50%
Clear communications	21	42%
Broader search, deeper pool	23	46%
Faster time-to-appointment	26	52%
Green solution	19	38%
Easy	21	42%
Can make your job As more dynamic	24	48%
Expedites the hiring process	24	48%
None	6	12%

From the above table we can analyze that there are many benefits of using digital platform for recruitment process. But the most common benefits are Faster time-to-appointment and Cost-effective.

Drawbacks of Digital recruitment process

Drawbacks	No. of respondents	Percentage
No face to face interaction	31	62%
low Internet penetration	10	20%
Cannot solely depend on data	24	48%
Difficult to measure effectiveness	20	40%
Informal	11	22%
Attraction fraudulent applicants	28	56%
Costs can spiral	14	28%
None	1	2%

From the above table we can see that the most common drawback for not using or reducing the usage of digital recruitment process is No face to face interaction and Attraction Fraudulent applicants.

Digital recruitment convenient for following job position

Every technology has its limitation and e-recruitment is not an exception. Through survey it has been identified that there are some limitations that organization face during hiring employee for certain position. It's been analyzed that digitalized tool is not appropriate for hiring employees working at lower-level position, blue collar employees as well as high position executive level employees.

Lower level or blue collar employees have skills that cannot be evaluated using online tests as well as technology is a limitation for this employees.

High position employees at the other hand are the one which need to be interviewed using personalized touch that is face to face interviews to attract them towards the organization.

FINDINGS

- 1) Almost 88% of Recruiters use digital platform for talent acquisition in their organization.
- 2) There are 12% of respondents who do not use e-recruitment as it is an inappropriate tool for small organizations.
- 3) Amongst various techniques Telephonic interview, Social Networks and Online Recruitment Sites are mostly used tools for generating the pool of potential candidates and identifying right candidate at right job.
- 4) Search and shortlist the right candidates is the most influential factor for using digital platform for recruitment.
- 5) The most common benefit for the use of Digital Recruitment process is it's speedy and cost-effective technique which reduces the burden of HR department.

- 6) Factors that limit/ reduce the use of e-recruitment is no face to face interaction/ personal touch and it attracts fraudulent applicants which is one of the biggest concern that organization faces.

CONCLUSION

- On the basis of this research, we can conclude that the use of latest technology in recruitment process can cause a real improvement, which focus on identify right candidate at right position by reducing the headcount form the large candidate pool. There are different organization that use digital recruitment process for different benefits.
- The effectiveness of digitalization can vary depending upon the size of the organization, as it is not appropriate to hire employees on lower-level positions.
- Introducing digital platform in recruitment process has many advantages for the organizations in the talent acquisition but research about this is insufficient. The major advantages include time savings, reduction in cost, reaching a broader audience and more accurate and detailed information about applicants.
- With the use of analysis and interpretations we can conclude that digitalized recruitment process has reduced the use of traditional recruitment process. Moreover, by data collection, it was also identified that, there are some flaws in the present e-recruitment system which can be balanced using traditional methods.
- Hence, we can say digital recruitment process is one of the most evolving part of organization as it gives the competitive

advantage to get potential / right candidate at right job.

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